

BMF CP97: The roles of health information-seeking ability and e-health literacy in illness response capability and health checkup frequency

AISDL Team

September 30, 2024

“Innovation can help Kingfisher conserve energy while maintaining a sense of tranquility, which is suitable for an increasingly advanced age with diminishing physical strength.”

—In “Innovation”; [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

[COLLABORATIVE PROJECT]

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How are health information-seeking ability and e-health literacy associated with illness response capability?
- How are health information-seeking ability and e-health literacy associated with the frequency of health checkups?

1.2. Materials

The granular interaction thinking of mindsponge theory will be used for the conceptual development of this study, while Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be used for statistical analysis [1-4]. The dataset comprises responses from 9775 people living in Qazvin province, Iran, between January and April 2022 [5]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [6]. For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/13859258>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis shows that health information-seeking ability and e-health literacy are positively associated with the capability of responding to illness. However, the moderation effect of e-health literacy on the relationship between health information-seeking ability and illness response capability (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The estimated posterior distributions

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps for registering to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institution email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**

AISDL members who have joined this project: Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

[1] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOC3WHZ2B3>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8367405102/>

[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum*

and information theories. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>

[4] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4922461>

[5] Pakpour AH, et al. (2023). Large-scale dataset on health literacy, sleep hygiene behaviors, and mental well-being in the general population of Qazvin, Iran. *Data in Brief*, **48**, 109072. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109072>

[6] La VP, Vuong QH. (2019). bayesvl: Visually Learning the Graphical Structure of Bayesian Networks and Performing MCMC with 'Stan'. *The Comprehensive R Archive Network*. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/bayesvl/index.html>

[7] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6>

